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Engineering curriculum development

Socialization, soft skills and professional identity construction

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ABSTRACT

Since October 2015, CESI's school of engineering has implemented a project-based learning curriculum in its combined work-studies engineering programme. A previous research study, led by CESI's Education Science Laboratory, showed that before this curricular shift, CESI's engineering apprentices developed their professional identity mainly through projects carried out during in-company periods. With this new study, we wished to analyse the impact of the new learning environment on students' professional identity formation. Could the new curriculum enhance their professional identification and sense of becoming during school periods?

We first set up indicators to assess the impact of the curriculum on professional identity development, and conducted both quantitative and qualitative surveys. Our enquiries showed the following results: the key roles of group work, as well as tutors and students themselves in the setting of professional rules in the classroom so that school projects could act as boosters to their self-recognition as novice professionals. The opportunities given to develop self-directedness and metacognitive skills appeared as other key elements in the development of a sense of "becoming" at school. The question of expertise or the prominence of soft skills as pillars to their identity also emerged as a central issue in their development.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills; Curriculum Development; Engineering Education Research

Keywords: Project-based learning; Professional identity formation; engineering skills development; soft skills

INTRODUCTION

CESI is a multi-centre French graduate school of engineering, originally created in 1958 as a Continuing Education School of Engineering. It pioneered introducing apprenticeship for higher education, and now about nine hundred freshmen students

each year enrol in its combined work-studies engineering programme, in thirteen cities all over France. This three-year combined work and study degree in Engineering, accessible after two years of scientific or technical higher education, leads to the equivalent of a Master in engineering. Since October 2015, and after two years of instructional design by a team of lecturers and course designers, CESI has implemented a project-based learning curriculum in this degree. In the new curriculum, students work in teams of five to six, and carry out multidisciplinary two-to-five week projects, in collaborative learning spaces. Each team has its own space with networked laptops, their own screen and a whiteboard, and five to six teams work in the same room. Lecturers seldom get to lecture anymore and are now labelled *tutors*: they guide the teams, set milestones, and can circulate amongst learning spaces and work with individual students as well as teams. Classrooms are adjacent to *Fablabs*, where students can experiment hands-on learning. This PBL curriculum was designed to be closer to professional practice and prepare future engineers to work in teams and communicate with ease, be adaptive, play a bigger role in their own training. It was intended to reduce the gap between the knowledge they acquire in their engineering school education and their actual in-company role.

1 RESEARCH QUESTION

A previous research study[1], led by CESI's Education Research Laboratory, showed that before this curricular evolution, the professional identity construction of CESI's engineering apprentices occurred mainly during key projects in their companies. Indeed, they were asked to identify turning points in their curriculum that influenced their transition from students to engineers. The 48 students who took part to this previous study pinpointed in-company projects as key moments where they developed project management and teamwork skills, as well as the confidence to label themselves "engineers", thanks to the recognition of their skills by their tutors and peers.

Through this research project, we wish to study the impact of the curricular shift and new learning environment on student's professional identity formation: can the new curriculum, thanks to its teamwork and PBL focus, enhance professional identification and sense of becoming at school? To what extent and through which specific media?

2 SUPPORTING LITERATURE

2.1 Professional identity

Professional identity is an ongoing, iterative, process that is influenced by social interactions, work or training environments, and personal identity [2]. This social "becoming" [3] is related not only to the development of work skills, but also to the development of a sense of belonging, and the recognition, by learners, peers and supervisors, of the learners' abilities and legitimacy. It then implies interactions, and sometimes tensions between a provisional self [3] -a self-projection of one's ideal identity-, one's work representations, and a social, prescribed identity (other people's expectations). Our first mission was thus to determine which indicators could be used to "measure" the professional identity formation of these engineering students and could thus help assess the impact of the new curriculum and learning environment on this process.

2.2 Student dispositions, engineering skills and learning environment

Previous studies show that a training environment that wishes to foster a sense of "becoming" should allow students to experiment with practices and self-images [3] by

developing self-reflexivity as well as interpersonal skills like communication. There also seems to have been a shift in industry expectations from expertise in a very specific discipline to more generic and transferable skills for future engineers: their jobs will require adaptive skills. In a professional context that is subjected to technological changes, they will need to be even more creative, innovative and able to deal with new forms of organizations [4]. Expertise, “mastery” as Scanlon calls it [3] is only a “momentary illusion”, while soft skills are assets that companies wish our graduate engineers could develop during their studies. Hence learning how to learn, who you are and such concepts as collective thinking seem to be key interpersonal & self-management skills, i.e. “soft skills”.

Soft skills are supposedly more developed by active learning than by traditional lectures [5]. However, in the process of professional identity formation, the type of pedagogy used in the programme is not the only element that has an impact on the students. Indeed, the actual interactions between these specific students’ dispositions -i.e. their action patterns, their motivation, cognitive capacities, values, expectations- and the curricular environment are key. Indeed, students have their own ideas of how school should prepare them to become their “ideal selves” [6]; i.e. professional engineers, so they will engage in the process according to the experienced “value” of the programme related to their own expectations [7]. As Dahlgren puts it [8], “people impact education” as much as it impacts them.

2.3 Curricular shift and professional identity construction

The new curriculum was designed as a transition between school and company, aiming at integrating disciplinary and professional knowledge. Through team project work, problem-solving loops, and the project leader role to assume in turns, the curriculum designers wished students to practice being engineers at school, to rehearse their provisional selves. The aim of our study is to analyse how the students *actually* experience the curriculum. So does it really boost students’ sense of becoming and confidence as future engineers? Does it allow them to practice critical reflection on their development? How does it consider their dispositions?

3 HYPOTHESES

Our first hypothesis is that students probably experience transition levers in this curriculum, but these levers might differ from what curriculum designers had intended, and even differ from one student to another. We want to enquire what these *actual* levers are.

The interrelations between learner dispositions and the curriculum also probably influence the impact of the curriculum on the learners’ construction of their professional identities, so we want to enquire potential transitional profiles that may emerge and the main mutual influences between dispositions and curricular tools.

The curriculum should also be questioned as a lever to develop personal identity and learner identity as well as professional identity, as the three seem deeply interconnected, especially through the lens of “soft skills”.

4 METHODOLOGY

4.1 Exploratory surveys

A preliminary study was conducted that consisted in an analysis of the curriculum referential, three interviews with the curriculum designers, and test interviews with two students and two tutors from the same CESI centre. This study aimed at four main goals:

- Understanding what the school expectations were in terms of their graduate engineers' skills;
- Understanding what the school expectations were in terms of the impacts of the curriculum on students;
- Starting to define measurement indicators of professional identity development of these engineering students and the impact of the curriculum on this development;
- Testing our interview guides

The data gathered during these different stages allowed us to define the following criteria, to assess the impact of the curriculum on professional identity formation:

- Internal indicators:
 - Student self-expression/identification to a role/position as an engineer;
 - Student self-confidence in engineering missions/ posture ;
 - Conscience of their acquisitions and self-reflexivity;
 - Developed self-directedness.
- External indicators :
 - Acquisition of key engineering skills: problem solving, team and project management, innovation and interpersonal skills (Skills deemed “key” by both students, tutors and designers according to the preliminary study).

4.2 Longitudinal studies

We combined two approaches to gather data to assess our criteria, define the curricular impact, and analyse evolutions and differences between centres, group tutors, specialities, and genders.

A quantitative approach, based on questionnaires to the 900 students in the curriculum, upon their arrival and on years two and three of the curriculum (year three starts in September 2017, so the survey is ongoing). This approach allowed us to gather data on the evolution of their projections as engineers, on their experience in the programme and the evolutions of their “becoming”, as well as on the actual levers of development experienced, according to different variables related to environmental factors.

A qualitative approach based on interviews with 30 students and 10 tutors from 6 different learning centres, is used to study the interrelation between student dispositions and curricular impact on the students' transitions.

5 RESULTS

5.1 Key moments

So far, the results analysed take into account the students' experience after a year and a half (out of three) in the learning programme. Students mentioned, both in interviews and in questionnaires¹, the oral evaluations they take at the end of each project as very realistic rehearsals of their skills and postures as future engineers. These evaluations, often organised as role-plays, are reported by students to make them «feel like» engineers, and increase their self-confidence as future engineers. For students interviewed who mention previous difficulties with oral interaction and public speaking, these oral evaluations as well as constant group work in the projects

¹ When specifically asked about « what tools, methods, situations in the school learning programme make you feel like/act like an engineer?»

are qualified as having a positive impact not only on their professional life in the company, but on their personality and overall behaviour towards other people.

Group problem solving stages involving calculations, modelling and prototyping are also mentioned as key elements in the approach, as well as the iterative problem solving method, because students feel these are effective tools they can use in the company, and most of them already use them in their companies. When projects lead to the actual implementation of a solution or to the actual development of a product, students mention the impact on both their motivation and self-confidence. After a year and a half in this active learning environment, most students still consider the company as the main environment to foster their sense of “becoming” and still rate the value of the school programme according to which tools, methods etc. experienced at school they actually use in their companies. However, they are able to pinpoint what activities and tools in the curriculum are key to their development, and when asked about it, they can even mention the generic skills they feel they have developed thanks to this methodology: communication and organizational skills mostly.

5.2 Socialization

Socialization through interpersonal interactions is confirmed as a lever to boost self-confidence, as well as acquire knowledge and project management skills. For example, throughout the first year, students were asked² about their confidence in their ability to carry out and succeed in the current project, and their confidence in their group to carry out and succeed in the current project. When only 40% of the students said they felt rather or fully confident they could individually succeed in carrying out the second project, 50% said they were rather or fully confident they would succeed as a group. Then on project 4 -out of 6 each year-, 55% of the respondents mention being rather or fully confident they could individually succeed, and 65.5% being rather or fully confident they could succeed as a group (see *Figure 1*).

Fig. 1. Role of group work in confidence, example of project 4

² Questionnaire based survey sent to students from 6 different centres, on three different projects throughout the year, with an average of a hundred respondents.

This development of overall confidence needs to be compared to data from later projects, to see if the increased confidence is still developing or was only related to the subject of project 4, but what is constant in both surveys is the higher confidence rate as a group rather than as individuals. In interviews, students mention the group as a way to acquire knowledge, as well as a way to feel “secure”, which can explain the data collected in the questionnaire.

However, tensions do arise from group-work as well, and almost 20% of 2nd year students³ mention “the group” as a difficulty, particularly when conflictual situations arise when not all group members share the same engagement in school projects. Both students and tutors evoke group work as a difficulty during interviews when one or several group members do not “play along” the project simulations. What is striking is that 32% of the second year apprentices who had had previous experience of in-company work did have trouble with group work at school, which is a lot higher than the average score. Students expressed that simulated projects at school were more difficult to engage in than “real” projects and that teamwork at school could be more difficult to handle than teamwork in the company. Working with trainees who are not their supervisors, can make it difficult for them to play along and actually lead a project and organize work. Trainees can judge this lack of actual hierarchy demotivating, or sometimes fear the judgement of their peers.

5.3 Expertise or soft skills?

Students, when they enter the programme, expect more from their company in terms of professional development than they expect from the school (see *Table 1*):

Table 1. Students’ expectations (start of the programme)⁴

Expectations	At school	In company
Develop professional skills	79%	90%
Be guided with professional project	45%	53%
Co-construction of professional identity through interactions	35%	58%
Gain scientific knowledge	72%	44%

What is striking is that the students that have high expectations in terms of scientific acquisitions towards the school are the students who express more dissatisfaction at the end of year 1. Whether they see the engineer as a scientific expert or as a multi-skilled project manager, students will engage accordingly in the curriculum because some think the school projects -that do not aim at scientific expertise- are not adequate to prepare them for their future jobs. Tutors can play a major role here in explaining the value of the soft skills developed, and explaining the learning theories behind the curriculum, and telling students what they can expect in terms of professional development. Results showed that with the guidance of tutors who

³ 211 respondents, from 6 different centres in France, at the beginning of year two, when asked about their major difficulties at school during year 1. Several answers were possible.

⁴ 533 respondents, from 9 different centres in France, at the beginning of year one when asked about their expectations from the school and from their company. Several answers were possible.

practice and encourage such reflexive processes, students are more engaged, and more satisfied with the curriculum.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

It seems so far that students' attitudes depend considerably on the tutors' roles and not only on the students' dispositions : whether tutors see themselves and position themselves as scientific experts or as guides for the students' professional development and show the links between school projects and students' missions in their companies, tutors can change the impact of the school curriculum. Tutoring and teaching are very different activities, requiring different skills so tutors need to adapt to the new curriculum as well. The key here is whether the value of the soft skills acquired is mentioned or not, whether the tutoring is helping students take a step back from technical and scientific acquisitions or not. Both tutors and students can act on the situation and decide to set professional rules in the classroom, and encourage professional engagement in the projects. Indeed, with the provisional results we gathered so far, we noticed the emergence of one transitional profile: students who are very engaged in the process, and who have more self-reflective abilities, who assign professional goals to the school projects and who use the group to develop their professional identity. These students happen to be older and have had two to five years of work experience as technicians before "going back to school". The majority of other apprentices do not (yet?) view the school periods as opportunities to learn their future job, but rather as a way to build their social network and personal identity. The students who do not have previous work experience, but still perceive what professional skills they can gain from school, are students who set achievement criteria for themselves, monitor their learning and try to relate school projects to company realities. Therefore, students' ability to manage their acquisitions according to their own goals and capacities and the opportunities that the very programme gives students to develop their self-directedness and other metacognitive skills is central. Professional identity formation can be described as the becoming of a self-reflexive individual, and for this to happen, every student's goal, expectations and experience should be made clear, discussed and explained. Our future enquiries will thus focus even more on tutoring and self-directedness development, to try to analyse how the curriculum can help students reflect on what type of professional engineers they wish to be and how school can help them do it.

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